

Uṣṇīṣa-vijayā-dhāraṇī: The Complete Sanskrit Text Based on Nepalese Manuscripts

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International Journal of Buddhist Thought & Culture Vol. 30. No.2 (December 2020):147–167

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<https://doi.org/10.16893/IJBTC.2020.12.31.2.147>

The day of submission: 2020.9.30.

Completion of review: 2020.12.17.

Final decision for acceptance: 2020.12.24.

Abstract

While the Uṣṇīṣavijayā tradition received considerable scholarly attention regarding its Central and East Asian aspects, examinations of native South Asian evidence have been sparse. This paper offers now the first critical edition and translation of the Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī as it survives in Sanskrit manuscripts. Using ten Nepalese witnesses, the text with the nidāna, dhāraṇī and kalpa sections is presented, which throws light on key ritual practices involving caitya deposits of various materials to provide longevity.

Key words: *Uṣṇīṣavijayā, dhāraṇī, critical edition, Nepal, manuscripts*

Introduction

As previously noted, the original Sanskrit *dhāraṇī sūtra* of the *Uṣṇīṣavijayā* remains largely unstudied (Chandra 1980, 125; Yuyama 2000, 165).¹ In this text the *dhāraṇī* is introduced by an opening part (*nidāna*) and followed by ritual instructions (*kalpa*) along with an enumeration of the benefits of use. The first portion and final colophon of what appears to be this scripture was printed in Devanāgarī (Müller and Nanjio 1884, 34-35) after an elusive book,² where the text is titled *Sarvatathāgatoṣṇīṣavijayā-nāma-dhāraṇī-kalpasahitā*.³ The *dhāraṇī* itself was studied on the basis of a Nepalese *Saptavāra* manuscript (Yuyama 2000).⁴ It should be mentioned that the *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī*, except for its spell section, is different from and much shorter than the extensive *Sarvagatipariśodhana-Uṣṇīṣavijayā-nāma-dhāraṇī* published recently (Unebe 2015).⁵ The *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* survives in Chinese⁶ and Tibetan⁷ canonical versions where the *kalpa* section is considerably longer than in the Sanskrit transmission.

Manuscripts selected

There are dozens of manuscripts preserving the *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* in South Asia, more precisely in Nepal.⁸ This text is transmitted primarily in collections, mostly the *Saptavāra* and *Dhāraṇīsaṃgraha*,⁹ but some individual manuscripts exist, too. The present edition is based upon ten paper¹⁰ manuscripts: five *Dhāraṇīsaṃgraha*, three *Saptavāra* and a miscellaneous collection, furthermore an individual witness.¹¹

Sigla

A: Cambridge University Library Ms. Add.1326.¹² A *Dhāraṇīsaṃgraha* manuscript, 225 paper leaves, dated to NS 839/1719 CE in the colophon. See Bendall (1883, 49–50) and Hidas (2021). The *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* is found at 136v–138r.

B: University of Tokyo Library Ms. 201.¹³ A *Dhāraṇīsaṃgraha* manuscript, 201

paper leaves, ca. 19th century. See Matsunami (1965: 81). The *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* is found at 14v–17r.

- C: University of Tokyo Library Ms. 192.¹⁴ A *Saptavāra* manuscript, 38 paper leaves (*nīlapattra*), dated to NS 909/1789 CE in the colophon. See Matsunami (1965: 78). The *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* is found at 11r–15r.
- D: Asha Archives, Kathmandu Ms. 2507. A *Dhāraṇīsaṃgraha* manuscript, 178 paper leaves, dated to NS 1001/1881 CE in the colophon. The *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* is found at 121r–122v.
- E: University of Tokyo Library Ms. 197.¹⁵ A *Saptavāra* manuscript, 24 paper leaves, dated to NS 993/1873 CE in the colophon. See Matsunami (1965, 80). The *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* is found at 8v–11v.
- F: University of Tokyo Library Ms. 419.¹⁶ A *Dhāraṇīsaṃgraha* manuscript, 312 paper leaves, dated to NS 912/1792 CE in the colophon. See Matsunami (1965, 149). The *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* is found at 229v–231v.
- G: National Archives Kathmandu Ms. NAK 3/641=NGMPP A 131–10. A *Dhāraṇīsaṃgraha* manuscript, 383 paper leaves, ca. 19th century. The *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* is found at 147v–148v.
- H: Cambridge University Library Ms. Add.1343.¹⁷ A *dhāraṇī* and *stotra* manuscript, 71 paper leaves, dated to NS 783/1663 CE in the colophon. See Bendall (1883: 60–61). The *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* is found at 10v–13v with its last folio missing.
- I: British Library Endangered Archives Programme Ms. EAP 676/10/7.¹⁸ A *Saptavāra* manuscript, 23 paper leaves, ca. 19th century. The *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* is found at 11v–14v.
- J: British Library Endangered Archives Programme Ms. EAP 790/14/8.¹⁹ An individual *Uṣṇīṣavijayā* manuscript, 5 paper leaves with an illustration, ca. 19th century.

Manuscript affinities and editorial policy

A statistical analysis shows that two groups can be distinguished among the ten manuscripts selected: ACEF and BDIJ.²⁰ Manuscripts G and H stand somewhat apart from both of these but are apparently closer to ACEF. Although the ACEF(GH) group seems to provide better readings in most cases, this cluster cannot always be preferred, most likely because of contamination. Thus, when orthography, grammar, syntax or context requires, variants from the BDIJ group have been chosen, too.

Normalizations

The following phenomena have been normalized without indication:

- variations between *alā, iī, ulū, elai, n/ṇ, ś/ṣ/s, r/l, j/y, t/n, kṣal/kṣya, chal/ccha, ṣal kha* and *ā/o, a/e, elai, o/au*
- final *anusvāras* before vowels or at the end of sentences and homorganic nasals in place of *anusvāras*
- degeminations in ligature with semivowel (e.g., *satva* for *sattva*)
- geminations after *r*
- missing or superfluous *r*-s including the insertion of *r* before double consonants
- missing or superfluous *anusvāras, visargas, avagrahas* and *daṇḍas*
- variations between double forms (e.g., *jaya jaya*) and numbered repetition (e.g., *jaya 2*) in the *dhāraṇī*
- open sandhi and other sandhi variations

Symbols and abbreviations

corr. correction

om. omission

ac. ante correctionem

pc. post correctionem

<...> folio number

M&N. selected variants from Müller and Nanjio 1884, 34–35

Tib. selected variants as reflected in the Tibetan version of D 595

Chin. selected variants as reflected in the Chinese version of T 978

A critical edition

oṃ²¹ namo bhagavatyai āryoṣṇīṣavijayāyai²² | evaṃ mayā śrutam ekasmin samaye bhagavān sukhāvatyām²³ dharmasamgiti²⁴ mahāguhya²⁵ prāsāde²⁶ viharati sma | sukhapraṭiṣṭhito²⁷ bhagavān²⁸ amitāyus²⁹ tathāgata³⁰ āryāvalokiteśvaraṃ³¹ bodhisattvaṃ³² mahāsattvaṃ āmantrayate³³ sma | santi kulaputra³⁴ duḥkhitāḥ³⁵ sattvā³⁶ nānāvādhiparipīḍitā³⁷ alpāyuṣkās³⁸ teṣāṃ³⁹ arthāya⁴⁰ hitāya sukhāya⁴¹ imāṃ sarvatathāgatoṣṇīṣavijayā⁴²-nāma-dhāraṇīm⁴³ dhārayed⁴⁴ vācayed⁴⁵ deśayet⁴⁶ paryavāpnuyāt⁴⁷ parebhyaś ca vistareṇa⁴⁸ samprakāśayet⁴⁹ | dīrghāyuṣkāṇāṃ⁵⁰ upādāyeti⁵¹ | atha khalv⁵² āryāvalokiteśvaro⁵³ bodhisattvo⁵⁴ mahāsattva⁵⁵ utthāyāsanād ekāṃsam uttarāsaṅgaṃ kṛtvā⁵⁶ kṛtāñjalipuṭo⁵⁷ bhūtvā bhagavantam etad⁵⁸ avocat | deśayatu⁵⁹ bhagavān⁶⁰ sarvatathāgatoṣṇīṣavijayā⁶¹-nāma-dhāraṇīm deśayatu⁶² sugataḥ⁶³ | atha khalu bhagavān sarvavātiparśanmaṇḍalam⁶⁴ avalokya⁶⁵ samantāvalokitaśriyā⁶⁶-nāma-samādhiṃ samāpanna-r⁶⁷-imāṃ sarvatathāgatoṣṇīṣavijayā-nāma-dhāraṇīm bhāṣate⁶⁸ sma |

oṃ namo bhagavate⁶⁹ sarvatrailokya⁷⁰ prativiśiṣṭāya⁷¹ buddhāya te⁷² namaḥ | tadyathā | oṃ bhrūṃ bhrūṃ bhrūṃ⁷³ śodhaya 2 viśodhaya 2⁷⁴ asamasamantāva⁷⁵ bhāsaspharaṇa⁷⁶ gatigagane⁷⁷ svabhāvaviśuddhe | uṣṇīṣavijayāpariśuddhe⁷⁸ | abhiṣīncantu māṃ sarvatathāgatāḥ⁷⁹ sugatavara⁸⁰ vacanāmṛtābhiṣekair⁸¹ mahāmudrā⁸² mantrapadaih | oṃ āhara⁸³ 2 āyuḥsaṃdhāraṇi⁸⁴ śodhaya 2 viśodhaya 2 gaganasvabhāvaviśuddhe⁸⁵ | uṣṇīṣavijayāpariśuddhe⁸⁶ | sahasraraśmisaṃcodite⁸⁷ sarvatathāgatāvalokini⁸⁸ ṣaṭpāramitā⁸⁹ paripūraṇi⁹⁰ | sarvatathāgatamāte⁹¹ daśa⁹² bhūmipraṭiṣṭhite | sarvatathāgatahṛdayādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite⁹³ | oṃ mudre mudre⁹⁴ | mahāmudre⁹⁵ | vajrakāyasaṃhatana⁹⁶ pariśuddhe⁹⁷ | sarvakarmāvaraṇa⁹⁸ viśuddhe | pratinivartaya⁹⁹ mamāyurviśuddhe¹⁰⁰ | sarvatathāgatasaṃmayādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite¹⁰¹ | oṃ muni¹⁰² 2¹⁰³ mahāmuni¹⁰⁴ | vimuni 2 mahāvimuni¹⁰⁵ | mati 2 mahāmati | mamati¹⁰⁶ | sumati | tathatā¹⁰⁷ bhūtakoṭipariśuddhe viśphuṭa¹⁰⁸ buddhi¹⁰⁹ śuddhe | oṃ¹¹⁰ he he¹¹¹ | jaya 2 | vijaya 2¹¹² smara¹¹³ 2 sphara 2¹¹⁴ sphāraya 2 | sarvabuddhādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite¹¹⁵ | oṃ śuddhe 2 buddhe 2¹¹⁶ vajre 2 mahāvajre¹¹⁷ | vajragarbhe | jayagarbhe¹¹⁸ | vijayagarbhe¹¹⁹ | vajrajvālgarbhe | vajrodbhave¹²⁰ | vajrasambhave | vajre¹²¹ vajriṇi vajraṃ bhavatu¹²² mama śarīraṃ¹²³ sarvasattvānāṃ ca | kāyapariśuddhir¹²⁴ bhavatu mama¹²⁵ sarvagatipariśuddhis¹²⁶ ca¹²⁷ sarvatathāgatahṛdayādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite¹²⁸ |

sarvatathāgatās ca¹²⁹ samāśvāsayan¹³⁰ | om budhya¹³¹ 2 sidhya¹³² 2 bodhaya 2
vibodhaya 2¹³³ mocaya 2 vimocaya 2 śodhaya 2 viśodhaya 2 samantān mocaya
2¹³⁴ samantaraśmipariśuddhe¹³⁵ | sarvatathāgata¹³⁶ hṛdayādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite¹³⁷ |
om mudre 2¹³⁸ mahāmudre mahāmudrāmantrapade¹³⁹ svāhā |

iyam sā kulaputra sarvatathāgatoṣṇiṣavijayā¹⁴⁰-nāma-dhāraṇī mahā¹⁴¹ mṛtyudaṇḍanivāraṇī¹⁴²
pavitrā-m-agma¹⁴³ nāśani¹⁴⁴ likhitvā¹⁴⁵ bhūrjapatre¹⁴⁶ nyatra vā¹⁴⁷ kvacic¹⁴⁸
caityamadhye kumbham¹⁴⁹ āśritya¹⁵⁰ samsthāpya¹⁵¹ | maṇḍalam udārām¹⁵²
pūjām¹⁵³ kṛtvā pradakṣiṇam¹⁵⁴ sahasraṃ kartavyam¹⁵⁵ | yathāvibhavanūrūpataḥ¹⁵⁶
suvarṇapatre¹⁵⁷ nāma likhitvā¹⁵⁸ dharmadhātugarbhe¹⁵⁹ samsthāpya¹⁶⁰
sampūjya dharmadhātum cādareṇa vā¹⁶¹ | ārdramṛttikā vā¹⁶² kārayitvā
saptaika¹⁶³ viṃśati catvāriṃśat¹⁶⁴ śatavārām¹⁶⁵ sahasraṃ vā¹⁶⁶ sampūjya¹⁶⁷
cchatrapatākā¹⁶⁸ puṣpadhūpadīpagandha¹⁶⁹ naivedyādikaṃ¹⁷⁰ sarvapūjābhiḥ
pūjayet¹⁷¹ |¹⁷² imāṃ sarvatathāgatoṣṇiṣavijayā-nāma-dhāraṇīm vācayet¹⁷³ |
ante¹⁷⁴ dūrvākṣatena¹⁷⁵ caityamūrdhni¹⁷⁶ arcayet¹⁷⁷ | yasyaivam¹⁷⁸ kṛte¹⁷⁹
'parimitāyur¹⁸⁰ medhāvino¹⁸¹ bhaviṣyanti¹⁸² | dānaṃ¹⁸³ dātavyam¹⁸⁴ | sapta¹⁸⁵ dināyuh¹⁸⁶
saptamāsāyuh¹⁸⁷ pratyāgamiṣyati¹⁸⁸ | saptamāsāyuh¹⁸⁹ saptavarṣāṇi¹⁹⁰ jīvati |
saptavarṣāyuh saptatavarṣāṇi¹⁹¹ jīvati¹⁹² | paramāyuhśatam jīvati | smṛtīmān¹⁹³ bhavati¹⁹⁴ |
mahārogaparimukto¹⁹⁵ bhavati | śrīrāyurarthasampannaś ca bhavati¹⁹⁶ |¹⁹⁷

āryoṣṇiṣavijayā¹⁹⁸-nāma-dhāraṇī samāpta¹⁹⁹

Translation

Om veneration to the glorious noble *Uṣṇiṣavijayā*.

Thus have I heard, at one time the Bhagavān was dwelling in the Dharma Proclamation Great Secret Temple-Palace in Sukhāvati. The Bhagavān was delightfully abiding [there and] Amitāyus Tathāgata addressed the noble Avalokiteśvara Bodhisattva-Mahāsattva.²⁰⁰ “O son of good family, there are suffering beings, tormented by various illnesses, with a short lifespan.²⁰¹ One should uphold, recite, teach and master this *dhāraṇī* called the Topknot Victory of all Tathāgatas for their advantage, benefit and comfort, and manifest²⁰² it in detail to others for the sake of longevity.²⁰³” Then the noble Avalokiteśvara Bodhisattva-Mahāsattva arose from his seat, arranged his upper robe over

one shoulder, put his hands together respectfully and thus spoke to the Bhagavān: “May the Bhagavān teach the *dhāraṇī* called the Topknot Victory of all Tathāgatas; may the Sugata expound it.” Then the Bhagavān looked at the whole assembly circle, entered the [state of] concentration named Auspiciousness Beheld Everywhere and revealed this *dhāraṇī* called the Topknot Victory of all Tathāgatas.

Om veneration to the glorious Buddha distinguished in all the Three Worlds. Namely, om bhrūṃ bhrūṃ bhrūṃ, purge, purge, purify, purify, O Unequaled Enveloping Splendor Sparkle Destiny Sky, O the One of Purified Nature, O the One Purified by the Topknot Victory, let all Tathāgatas consecrate me with consecrations of the nectar of the excellent Sugata’s words along with great seals and mantrapadas, om bring, bring, O the One who Nourishes Life, purge, purge, purify, purify, O the One Purified by Sky Nature, O the One Purified by the Topknot Victory, O the One Impelled by Thousand Rays, O the One Beholding all Tathāgatas, O the One Fulfilling the Six Perfections, O Mother of all Tathāgatas, O the One Established in the Ten Stages, O the One Empowered by the Empowerment of the Heart of all Tathāgatas, om O Seal, O Seal, O Great Seal, O the One Purified by the Firmness of the Vajra Body, O the One Purged of all Obstructions Resulting from Actions, turn back for me O Life-purged One,²⁰⁴ O the One Empowered by the Empowerment of the Vow of all Tathāgatas, om muni muni, mahāmuni, vimuni vimuni, mahāvimuni, mati mati, mahāmati, mamati, sumati, O the One Purified by Truth and the True Goal, O the One Purged by a Burst Open Mind, om he he, triumph triumph, succeed succeed, recollect recollect, manifest manifest, expand expand, O the One Empowered by the Empowerment of all Buddhas, om O Pure One, O Pure One, O Awakened One, O Awakened One, O Vajra, O Vajra, O Great Vajra, O Vajra-essence, O Victory-essence, O Triumph-essence, O Vajra-flame-essence, O Vajra-born, O Vajra-produced, O Vajra, O the One with a Vajra, let my body become a vajra and that of all beings, let there be body-purification for me and purification of all destinies, O the One Empowered by the Empowerment of the Heart of all Tathāgatas, let all Tathāgatas provide encouragement, om awake awake, succeed succeed, awaken awaken, wake up, wake up, liberate liberate, release release, purge purge, purify purify, liberate completely, O the One Purified by an Enveloping Ray, O the One Empowered by the Empowerment of the Heart of all Tathāgatas, om O Seal O Seal, O Great Seal, O Great Seal and Mantrapada svāhā.

O son of good family, this *dhāraṇī* called the Topknot Victory of all Tathāgatas is the great averter of the rod of death, pure, the destroyer of sins. Having written it on birch bark²⁰⁵ or something else, it should be deposited in a pot²⁰⁶ inside a *caitya*. Having made a *maṇḍala* and a great *pūjā* it should be circumambulated a thousand times. According to one's means it should be written on gold leaf²⁰⁷ and should be placed in a Dharma relic shrine after worshipping the Dharma relic respectfully.²⁰⁸ Having prepared wet clay [sealings],²⁰⁹ seven [times] twenty-one [or] forty, and having worshipped [these] a hundred or a thousand times, [they] should be revered with parasols, banners, flowers, incense, lamps, fragrances, offerings and so on during all [kinds of] *pūjā*. One should recite this *dhāraṇī* called the Topknot Victory of all Tathāgatas. Finally, it should be honored with uncrushed *dūrva* leaves at the top of a *caitya*. For whom this is done, he will have an immeasurable lifespan and becomes a learned man.²¹⁰ A donation should be given.²¹¹ The one to live for seven days shall be revived for seven months; the one to live for seven months shall live for seven years;²¹² the one to live for seven years shall live for seventy years. He shall live for a highest hundred years. He will have full consciousness. He will be free from the great diseases. He will be endowed with auspiciousness, longevity and wealth.”²¹³

The noble *dhāraṇī* called the Topknot Victory of all Tathāgatas has ended.

Notes

- * Many thanks to Dr. Péter-Dániel Szántó for advice and an analysis of Tibetan versions and Dr. Gábor Kósa for an examination of Chinese sources.
- 1 Bühnemann (2014, 120) remarks that this text has been printed in a modern booklet in Nepal (unseen by the present author) containing the *Saptavāra* collection. Hiding in a longer *Dhāraṇīsamgraha* manuscript this text is also reproduced in facsimiles and a Devanāgarī transcript in Bhoosekar (2017, 342–347). For the Pali Uṅghissavijaya tradition in Southeast Asia—significantly different from the surviving Sanskrit texts. See Cicuzza (2018) and de Bernon (in the present issue).
 - 2 As the authors remark, this is “a book, probably published in China, but without a date. It is a ‘Collection of Miscellaneous Buddhist Sanskrit Texts.’” It is also noted that the only copy known to exist was acquired in Beijing and used to be in the possession of Max Müller. I have been unable to trace this publication.
 - 3 Note that such a title is unattested in the Nepalese manuscripts examined; rather, it follows those given in Sanskrit in Tibetan catalogues (see Ui et al. 1934, 104). Thus, it is likely that this *Sarvatathāgatoṣṇīṣavijayā-nāma-dhāraṇī-kalpasahitā* is somewhat different and, considering the printed page numbers referred to (pp. 69–75), perhaps is also longer than the *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* edited in the present paper. It cannot be completely excluded either that it is a back-translation from Tibetan.
 - 4 See also Yuyama (1997 and 2006). There are numerous studies on the *Uṣṇīṣavijayā* in its Central and East Asian contexts the survey of which is beyond the scope of the present article.
 - 5 The Chinese version of this scripture is listed as T 967 and the Tibetan as e.g., Derge 597. Note that this text is included in the *Lhan kar ma* catalogue of ca. 800 CE as no. 348 (Herrmann-Pfandt 2008, 195–196).
 - 6 Among the several *Uṣṇīṣavijayā* texts grouped together in the Taishō canon (T nos. 968–974, 978–979) it is T 978 which stands closest to the Nepalese tradition examined here. It was translated by Dharmadeva (Fatian) between 973–981 CE and titled *Foshuo yiqie rulai wusenisha zuisheng zongchi jing* (Scripture Spoken by the Buddha on the Most Victorious Dhāraṇī of the Uṣṇīṣa of all Buddhas).
 - 7 Among the various *Uṣṇīṣavijayā* texts grouped together in the *Kanjur* (e.g., Derge 594–596, 598) it is D 595 which stands closest to the Nepalese tradition examined here. It is titled *De bzhin gshegs pa thams cad kyi gtsug tor rnam par rgyal ba zhes bya ba'i gzungs rtog pa dang bcas pa* “The Dhāraṇī called Topknot Victory of all Tathāgatas along with a Ritual Manual.” This text is not included in the *Lhan kar ma* catalogue and no translators are named.
 - 8 See Matsunami (1965, 339), Tsukamoto et al. (1989, 67, 102) or the catalogues of the Nepalese-German Manuscript Cataloguing Project, the Asha Archives, Kathmandu and the Endangered Archives Programme located in London, for example.

- 9 On these compendiums see Bühnemann (2014) and Hidas (2021) respectively.
- 10 Two palm leaf witnesses have also been identified, yet these contain only the *dhāraṇī* itself and one is incomplete. For a complete source see Cambridge Add.1680.8.1 (studied in Hidas 2021) and for a single leaf NGMPP A 933/02 (=NAK 5/7493), exposures 247–248.
- 11 Some more sources have also been examined but are excluded from this edition because these do not seem to add much new information to the data already collected: University of Tokyo Library Mss. 191, 196, 198, 199, 211 and 418; Asha Archives Ms. 2566; Endangered Archives Programme Ms. EAP 790/15/9 and Bhosekar (2017).
- 12 <https://cudl.lib.cam.ac.uk/view/MS-ADD-01326/1>
- 13 http://picservice.ioc.u-tokyo.ac.jp/03_150219~UT-library_sanskrit_ms/MF13_24_012~MF13_24_012/?pageId=001
- 14 http://picservice.ioc.u-tokyo.ac.jp/03_150219~UT-library_sanskrit_ms/MF13_24_003~MF13_24_003/
- 15 http://picservice.ioc.u-tokyo.ac.jp/03_150219~UT-library_sanskrit_ms/MF13_24_008~MF13_24_008/
- 16 http://picservice.ioc.u-tokyo.ac.jp/03_150219~UT-library_sanskrit_ms/MF13_50_004~MF13_50_004/?pageId=001
- 17 <https://cudl.lib.cam.ac.uk/view/MS-ADD-01343/22>
- 18 <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP676-10-7#?c=0&m=0&s=0&cv=15&xywh=-1%2C-205%2C5315%2C3951>
- 19 <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP790-14-8#?c=0&m=0&s=0&cv=2&xywh=0%2C-153%2C3960%2C2945>
- 20 Out of ca. 175 variants the following groups of manuscripts occur most often: ABCDEFGIJ 17 (indicating H to be apart), AF 13, BDIJ 11, ABCDEFHIJ 10 (indicating G to be apart), ACEFGH 10, GH 5, ABCDEFIJ 5, BD 4, DIJ 4, ACEFG 4, ACDEFGHIJ 4, BDEIJ 4.
- 21 <A136v>, <B14v>, <C11r>, <D121r>, <E8v>, <F229v>, <G147v>, <H10v>, <I11v>, <J1v>
- 22 om̐ namo bhagavatyai āryoṣṇīṣavijayāyai] ACDFGH]pc]; om̐ namo ratnatrayāya | om̐ namaḥ śrībhagavatyai āryoṣṇīṣavijayāyai B, om̐ namo bhagavatyai āryaśrī-uṣṇīṣavijayāyai E, om̐ namo uṣṇīṣavijayāyai Hac, om̐ namo śrībhagavatyai āryoṣṇīṣavijayāyai I
- 23 sukhāvatyāṃ] ABCDEFGI; sukhāvatyāṃ mahānagaryāyāṃ H, sukhāvatyāṃ viharati sma | kathaṃ bhagavan J
- 24 -saṃgīti-] ABCDEGHIJ; -saṃgati F
- 25 -guhya-] ABCDEFGIJ; -gurya- H
- 26 -prāsāde] ABF; -prāsāde bhavane CEGH, -prāsāde bhagavān DIJ
- 27 sukhapraṭiṣṭhito] corr.; sukho praṭiṣṭhito ACEFG, sukhāvaṭiṣṭhite B, sukhapraṭiṣṭhite DJ, sukho praṣṭhito H, sukho praṭiṣṭhite I, sukhopaviṣṭo M&N, om. Tib.
- 28 -vān] ABCDEGHIJ; -vānn F

- 29 amitāyus] ABCDEFIJ; āmitābhas G, amṛtāyu H
 30 -ta] BDH; -to ACEFGIJ, tathāgato 'rhan samyaksambuddha M&NTib.
 31 <J2r>
 32 -sattvaṃ] ABCDEFHIJ; -sattvo G
 33 -yate BDG; -ye ACEFIJ, -te H
 34 -putra] ACDEFGHIJ; -putro B
 35 -tāḥ] BDEIJ; -tān AFGI, -tānām C, -tva H <C11v>
 36 -tvā] BDEGHIJ; -tvān AF, -tvānām C <B15r> <D121v>
 37 nānāvādhīparipīḍitā] J; nānāvādhīparipīḍitān AF, *om.* BDI, nāvādhīparipīḍitānām C,
 nānāvādhīparipīḍitāḥ E, nānāvādhīparimaṇḍitān G, nānāvādhīparipīḍitān H
 38 alpāyūṣkās] ABFHIJ; alpāyūṣkān CG, alpāyūṣkāḥ D, alpāyūṣkatā E, mandāyūṣkās M&N
 39 teṣām] ACEFGH; teṣām sattvānām BDIJ
 40 <H11r>
 41 sukhāya] ABCDEFHIJ; sukhāyara G
 42 <A137r> <I12r>
 43 dhāraṇīm] ABCDEFGIJ; *om.* H
 44 -yed] C; -yet AEFG, -ya BDIJM&N, -yata H
 45 vācayed] EH; vācayet AFG, vācaya BCDIJ
 46 -yet] ACEFGH; -ya BDIJ
 47 -nuyāt] ACEFGH; -nuhi B, -nuyā DIJ
 48 vistareṇa] ABCDEFGHI; saṃpravistareṇa *Eac, om.* J
 49 -yet] ACEFGH; -ya BDIJM&N <E9r>
 50 dīrghāyūṣkānām] ABCDFHIJ; dīrghāyūṣkatāṣkatām *Eac* dīrghāyūṣkatām *Epc*,
 dīrghārātram arthāya hitāya sukhāya ca bhaviṣyati G, paryāyaskandham M&N <F230r>
 51 upādāyati] ABCFHIJ; upānāyati D, upādāyati E, *om.* G
 52 khalv] ACEFH; khalv āyūṣmān BDIJ, khalu bhagavān G
 53 -ro] ABCDFGIJ; -ra EH
 54 -tvo] ABDFGJ; -tva CEHI
 55 -tva] CDGHIJ; -tvaḥ AEF, -tvo B
 56 ekāṃśam uttarāsaṅgaṃ kṛtvā] AF; *om.* BDEIJM&NTibChin, ekottarāsaṅgaṃ kṛtvā C,
 ekāṃ H, ekāṃśam uttarām G
 57 -puṭo] ABCDEFGIJ; -pulatva H
 58 <J2v>
 59 deśayatu] ABCDFIJ; tad deśayatu E, deśayantu GH
 60 -vān] DEGH; -van ABCFIJ
 61 <C12r>
 62 deśayatu] ABCDEFGIJ; deśayanti sma H
 63 -taḥ] BH; -ta ACEFGIJ
 64 <G148r>
 65 -lokya] ABCEFIJ; -loke DGH

- 66 -lokitaśriyā-] CG; -lokitaśriyā- A, -lokiśvara- B, -lokiteśvara- DIJ, -lokitaśriyaṃ E, -lokiteśriyā- F, -lokiteśvaraśriyā- H, -lokiśriyaṃ M&N
- 67 -panna-r-] ACF; -pannaḥ BDJ, -padya EM&N, -panna GI, -padyan H <H11v>
- 68 bhāṣate] BCEGIJ; bhāṣante AFH, bhāṣyate D
- 69 bhagavate] CDEGHJ; bhagavatyai ABFI
- 70 -trailokya-] ABCDFGIJ; -tathāgatatrailokya- E, -trailoke- H
- 71 -prativiśiṣṭāya] ACEFG; -pratiṣṭhitāya BJ, -pratiṣṭhāya D, prativiśiṣṭāya H, -prativiśṭāya I
- 72 te] ACDEFGHIJ; *om.* B
- 73 bhrūṃ bhrūṃ bhrūṃ] ABCDEFHJ; bhrūṃ bhrūṃ bhrūṃ bhrūṃ G, traṃ traṃ traṃ I
- 74 viśodhaya 2] ABCDEFGIJ; *om.* H <E9v> <I12v>
- 75 asamasamantāva-] ACDEFGHIJ; asamantāva- B
- 76 -spharaṇa-] ACEFGHIJ; -sphara- B, -sphuṭeraṇa- D
- 77 -gagane] ACFGI; -gagana- BDEH*pc*, -gana H*ac*, -gagane samudgate J <J3r>
- 78 <B15v> <C12v>
- 79 -tāḥ] ABDEFG; -tāṃ C, -ta H, -tā I, -taḥ J
- 80 -vara-] ABCDEFGHIJ; *om.* I
- 81 -śekair] ABCDEFHJ; -śeke G
- 82 -mudrā-] ACEFGH; *om.* BDIJ
- 83 āhara] ABCEFGIJ; āḥ hara DH
- 84 -aṇi] ABCDFGIJ; -iṇi EH
- 85 -svabhāvaśuddhe] ABCDGHJ; -sobhāvaśuddhe E, -svabhāvaśuddhe F
- 86 <F230v>
- 87 <H12r>
- 88 -āvalokini] ABCDEFHJ; -āvalokite G
- 89 -pāramitā-] ABCDEFGIJ; -pāyāramitā- H
- 90 -aṇi] ACFIJ; -iṇi BDEGH
- 91 -gatamāte] BCDJ; -gatamātre AEF, -gata- G, -tomāte H, -gatamātar I
- 92 daśa-] ABCDEFGIJ; daśami- H
- 93 -hṛdayādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite] AEFHG; -hṛyādadhīṣṭhite B*ac*, -hṛdayādhiṣṭhite B*pc*DIJ, -hṛdayānādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite C
- 94 mudre mudre] ABCDEFHI; muni 2 G, mudre J <A137v>
- 95 mahāmudre] ABCDEHIJ; mahāmahāmudre F, mahāmudrā G
- 96 -saṃhatana-] ABCDEFGIJ; -tana- H <C13r> <J3v>
- 97 -pariśuddhe] ABCDEFHJ; -saṃpariśuddhe G
- 98 -karmāvaraṇa-] ABCDEFGIJ; -kāyatena- H <E10r>
- 99 pratinivartaya] BCDIJ; pratinivartanāya AF, pratinivartasa E, pratinivartayā G, pratinivartiya H <D122r>
- 100 mamāyurviśuddhe] BCDHI; viśuddhe AF, mamāyurviśuddhe E, mamāyaviśuddhe G, mamāyupariśuddhe J
- 101 -samayādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite] ABDEFGIJ; -samayānādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite CH <I13r>

- 102 -ni] ABCDEFGIJ; -ne H
- 103 G adds (eyeskip) mahāmudrā vajrakāyaśaṃhatanasāṃparisuddhe | sarvakarmāvaraṇaviśuddhe |
pratīnivartayā mamāyuvīśuddhe | sarvatathāgatasamayādhiṣṭhite || oṃ muni 2
- 104 -ni] ABCDEFGIJ; -ne H
- 105 2 mahāvīmuni] ACEFG; *om.* BDHIJ
- 106 mamati] ACFGH; niyamamati B, yamati DI*ac*J, mama E, yaśamati I*pc*
- 107 tathatā-] ABCDEFGHI; tathāgata- J
- 108 viśphuṭa-] ACFH; niśphuṭa- BDIJ, viśphuṭa 2 E, viśphuṭi- G
- 109 -buddhi-] BDEIJ; -buddha- AF, -vi- CGH
- 110 oṃ] ACEFH; *om.* BDGIJ
- 111 he] ABCEFGH; ho DIJ
- 112 vijaya 2] ABCDEFGIJ; *om.* H
- 113 smara] ACDEFGHIJ; samara B
- 114 <H12v>
- 115 -buddhādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite] AF; -mudrāṇām adhiṣṭhite B, -mudrāṇām
adhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite CI, -mudrāṇām adhinādhiṣṭhite DH, -mudrādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite EG,
-mudrāṇādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite J
- 116 buddhe 2] ABCDFGHIJ; *om.* E <B16r>
- 117 mahāvajre] ABCDEGHIJ; mahāvajre suvajre F
- 118 jayagarbhe] ACEFH; *om.* BDGIJ <C13v>
- 119 vijayagarbhe] ABCDEHIJ; *om.* FGI
- 120 vajrodbhave] ABCDEFGIJ; vajrogadbhave H <J4r>
- 121 vajre] ACEFGH; *om.* BDIJ
- 122 vajraṃ bhavatu] CEGH; vajraṃ sambhavatu ABDFIJ
- 123 śarīraṃ] ABCDEFHIJ; saparivāraṃ G
- 124 -parisuddhir] ACDEFHIJ; -pariparisuddhir B, -parisuddhe G
- 125 mama] ABDFI; mama sarvadā CEGHJ
- 126 -gatiparisuddhiś] A*pc*.BCDFI; -gatiparisuriddhiś A*ac.*, -tiparisuddhi E,
-gatiparisuddham G, -gatipaśuddhi H*ac*, -gatiparisuddhi H*pc*
- 127 ca] AF; ca mama BCDGHIJ, *om.* E
- 128 sarvatathāgatahṛdayādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite] AF; *om.* BCDEGHIJ <F231r>
- 129 sarvatathāgatās ca] ABF; sarvatathāgatās ca māṃ CEG, sarvatathāgatā māṃ D,
sarvatathātās ca māṃ H, sarvatathāgatānāṃ IJ
- 130 samāśvāsayantu] ACDFGHIJ; samāspādayantu B, śvāsayantu E <E10v>
- 131 budhya] ABCDFGHI; buddhe E]
- 132 sidhya] ABCDFGHI; śuddhe E]
- 133 <I13v>
- 134 mocaya 2] ADEFGHIJ; mocaya BCI
- 135 <H13r>
- 136 tathāgata] A*pc*.BCDEFGHIJ; tatagathā A*ac.*

- 137 -hṛdayādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite] AEFGIJ; - hṛdayānādhiṣṭhānādhiṣṭhite CH,
-hṛdayādhiṣṭhite D
- 138 <C14r>
- 139 -mudrāmantrapade] DEFGHIJ; -mudrāmantrapadaḥ AF, -mudre mantrapade B,
-mudrāmantrapadāḥ C
- 140 <J4v>
- 141 mahā-] ACEFGHTib; *om.* BDIJ
- 142 -nivāraṇī] ACF; -haroya B, -harā DEI, -nivāriṇī GH, -nivāriṇī aparājitaḥarāya J
<G148v>
- 143 pavitrā-m-agma-] ACEFGTib; piḍā-m-agma- BDJ, paritrā-m-agma H, -ghanāśini I
- 144 -nāśanī] ACEFGHIJ; -nāśini BG, -vināśini D
- 145 likhitvā] BDEIJ; likhitā ACFH, litā G
- 146 -patre] ABCEFIJ; -patrapatre D, -patre vā G, -patraya H
- 147 vā] ABCDEFHIJ; *om.* G
- 148 kvacī] ABCDEFI; kvaci GH
- 149 caityamadhye kumbham] ABCDEFHIJ; caitye G
- 150 āśritya] ACDEFIJ; āsthāpa B, *om.* G, āśrite H. Tib.Chin. omit kumbham āśritya.
- 151 -sthāpya] ABCDEFGIJ; -sthāpe H
- 152 maṇḍalam udārām] ABCEF; maṇḍalamudrām DGI, maṇḍalamudāmām H,
maṇḍalamudrā- J. Tib.Chin. omit maṇḍalam
- 153 pūjām] ACEFGH; jāṃ B, lājām pūjām DI, -rājām pūjām J
- 154 -ṇam] ACEFGH; -ṇa BDIJ <A138r>
- 155 -vyam] ABCDEFHIJ; -vyā G
- 156 yathāvibhavanurūpataḥ] ABCDFHIJ; yathāpi bhagavān anurūpitaḥ E, yathā hi
bhagavān rūpataḥ G <H13v>
- 157 -patre] ABCDEFGIJ; -paṭu C, -prabhu H
- 158 nāma likhitvā] ACEFGIJ; nāvalilikhitvā B, *om.* D, nāmaṃ likhitvā H <B16v>
- 159 -garbhe] ABCDEFGIJ; *om.* H <I14r>
- 160 -sthāpya] ABCDEFGIJ; -sthāpe H <E11r>
- 161 -dhātuṃ cādareṇa vā] B; -dhātucodane vā AF, -dhātucodanām vā CG, *om.* D,
-dhātucodanena vā E, -dhātuvedanā vā H, -dhātucādareṇā vā I, -dhātusaṃcodalena J
- 162 ārdramṛttikā vā] A; mṛttikayo B, ārdramṛttikāyā C, *om.* D, ārdramṛtti F, ārdramṛttikāyā
EGH, āhamṛttikāyā I, cārdhamṛttikāyā J <C14v>
- 163 saptaika-] ACEFGH; saptā- BJ, *om.* D, sapta- I
- 164 catvāriṃśat] AF; catuścatvāriṃśac BI, caturcatvāri C, *om.* D, catuḥcatvāriṃśat E,
caturcatvāriṃśatāc G, catuḥcatvāriṃśat H, catuḥcatvāriṃ J
- 165 śatavārām] ABDFGIJ; śativārā C, vā E, saptavārā H
- 166 vā] ACEFGH*pc*IJ; *om.* BD, havā *Hac* <J5r>
- 167 sampūjya] ABCDEFIJ; sampūrya GH
- 168 cchatrapatakā] AFGH; patākācchattra- BIJ, cchatradhvajapatākā C, *om.* D,

- patākacchattradhvaja- E
- 169 -dīpagandha-] AEF \overline{GH} \overline{pc} ; -gandhadīpa- B, -dīpagandharva CH \overline{ac} , *om.* D, -gandhapradīpa- I, -dhvajapuṣpadhūpagandhapradīpa- J
- 170 -naivedyādikaṃ] ACEFIJ; -navidyādikaṃ B, *om.* D, -naivyadyādikaṃ GH
- 171 pūjayet] ACFGHJ; saṃpūjayet BEI, *om.* D
- 172 D omits suvarṇapatre nāma likhitvā dharmadhātugarbhe saṃsthāpya saṃpūjya dharmadhātucodane vā | ārdramṛttikā vā kārayitvā saptaikaviṃśati catvāriṃśat śatavārāṃ sahasraṃ vā saṃpūjya cchattrapatākā puṣpadhūpadīpagandhanaivedyādikaṃ sarvapūjābhīḥ pūjayet
- 173 vācayet] ACFGHJ; vācayitvā BEIJ, vācatvā D <F231v>
- 174 ante] ABCDEFGIJ; satyaṃ H
- 175 dūrvākṣatena] ABCDEFIJ; dūrvākṣas G, dūrvācchetena H
- 176 caityamūrdhni] AFG; caityamūrtim BI, caityamūrdhni-m- CEJ, caitye mūrtim D, caityamaddhir H
- 177 arcayet] ABCDEFIJ; mañcayet G, yacayet H
- 178 yasyaivaṃ] ACDEHIJ; yasyavaṃ B, tasyaivaṃ F, yasyaiva G
- 179 kṛte] ACDEFI; kṛta B, kṛtvā G, kṛtya H, kṛte saptamāsāyuh saptavarṣāyusaṃ jīvati J. Tib.Chin. omit suvarṇapatre nāma likhitvā dharmadhātugarbhe saṃsthāpya saṃpūjya dharmadhātum cādareṇa vā | ārdramṛttikā vā kārayitvā saptaikaviṃśati catvāriṃśat śatavārāṃ sahasraṃ vā saṃpūjya cchattrapatākā puṣpadhūpadīpagandhanaivedyādikaṃ sarvapūjābhīḥ pūjayet | imāṃ sarvatathāgatoṣṇiṣavijayā-nāma-dhāraṇiṃ vācayet | ante dūrvākṣatena caityamūrdhni arcayet | yasyaivaṃ kṛte
- 180 'parimitāyur-] EIJ; 'paramitāyu- ABFG, parikṣiṇāyūṣo vā B, 'parimitāyunā C, *om.* DChin, aparamṛtāyu- H
- 181 -medhāvino] ABCF \overline{H} ; *om.* BDI, medhā E, -dharmamedhāvino G, -medhāvira J
- 182 -anti] ABCDEF \overline{H} ; *om.* D, -ati GIJ
- 183 dānaṃ] ACFGH; vibhūtidānaṃ B, *om.* D, dānaṃ suvarṇādikaṃ EJ, dānaṃ svarṇādikaṃ I. D omits 'paramitāyurmedhāvino bhaviṣyanti || dānaṃ
- 184 dātavyam] ABCE \overline{FHI} J; *om.* D, dattavyam G. Ms. H ends here as the last folio is missing. Tib.Chin. omit dānaṃ dātavyam
- 185 D omits 'parimitāyurmedhāvino bhaviṣyanti || dānaṃ dātavyam | sapta-
- 186 saptadināyuh] ACDF; yathā saptadināyuh BI, saptadināni yat E, *om.* GJ
- 187 saptamāsāyuh] ABCE \overline{FGI} \overline{pc} ; saptasāyuh D, *om.* Iac]
- 188 J omits saptadināyuh saptamāsāyuh pratyāgamiṣyati
- 189 Tib.Chin. omit saptamāsāyuh pratyāgamiṣyati | saptamāsāyuh
- 190 <C15r>
- 191 saptavarṣāṇi jīvati | saptavarṣāyuh saptatavarṣāṇi] AEF; saptavarṣāyusaṃ B, saptavarṣāṇi jīvati | saptavarṣāṇi saptatavarṣāyuh C, *om.* D, saptavarṣāṇi jīvati G, saptavarṣāyusaṃ jīvati <I14v> saptavarṣāyuh saptatavarṣāyuh(\overline{pc} . ṣaṃ) I, saptatavarṣāyusaṃ J
- 192 G omits saptavarṣāyuh saptatavarṣāṇi jīvati

- 193 smṛtimān] ACEFIJ; *om.* BD, savamantimān *Gac*, samantimān *Gpc* <E11v>
- 194 paramāyuhśataṃ jīvati | smṛtimān bhavati] ACEFGIJ; *om.* BD
- 195 mahārogaparimukto] G; mahārogaparimukto AF, yaṃcānantaryavinirmukto B, mahāghorogaparimukto C, *om.* D, sarvarogavimukto E, rogavinirmukto I, sarvarogairvinirmukto J <J5v>
- 196 bhavati] ABCFGIJ; *om.* D, bhaver iti kṛtvā bhūvan iti E. D omits saptamāsāyuh saptavarṣāṇi jīvati | saptavarṣāyuh saptavarṣāṇi jīvati | paramāyuhśataṃ jīvati | smṛtimān bhavati | mahārogaparimukto bhavati | śrīrāyurarthasampannāś ca bhavati || ||
- 197 BDI add idam avocad bhagavān āttamanā(ātmanās te I) āyushmān(*om.* D) āryāvalokiteśvaro bodhisattvo mahāsattvaḥ sā ca sarvātī parṣat sadevamānuṣāsura(-garuḍa- I)gandharvaś(-gandharvāsuraś D) ca loko bhagavato bhāṣitam <B17r> <D122v> abhyanandann iti
- 198 āryoṣṇīṣavijayā-] ABCDFGJ; iti śrī-āryoṣṇīṣavijayā EI
- 199 samāptā] FG; samāptaḥ A, parisamāptaḥ BD, parisamāpta C, samāptam E, parisamāptā | śubham | ye dharmā... I, parisamāptam | ye dharmā ādi | śubhamaṅgalaṃ bhavantu sarvadākāle śubham J
- 200 It is not straightforward how the *nidāna* should be interpreted. The Sanskrit transmission appears to conflate two versions, namely, that it is the Buddha who teaches this *dhāraṇī* and that it is Amitāyus who does so. In either case it is Avalokiteśvara who requests the sermon. Note that both Bhagavān and Sugata normally refer to the Buddha. In the Tibetan version it is Amitāyus who gives the sermon while in the Chinese it is the Buddha.
- 201 Longevity appears to be a core benefit of the *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī*. Cf. *Aparimitāyuh-sūtra* (Konow 1916).
- 202 Note the variations between the imperative and optative in this sentence. The imperative is problematic as it would imply that it is Avalokiteśvara who is requested to give the teaching.
- 203 Literally: “long-lived ones.”
- 204 This part of the *dhāraṇī*, *pratiniṣvartaya mamāyurvīśuddhe* (and its variants), looks problematic to interpret.
- 205 Although no birch bark copies of the *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* are known to survive in South Asia, note the Gilgit-Bamiyan manuscript of the *Sarvagatiparisodhana-Uṣṇīṣavijayā-nāma-dhāraṇī* (Uebe 2015).
- 206 On *caitya* deposits see recently Drewes (2007, esp. 126ff) and Salomon (2009).
- 207 Although no gold plates with the *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* are known to survive in South Asia, note those with Pali *suttas*, the *Pañcaviṃśatikā Prajñāpāramitā* and *Mahāpratisarā* mantras unearthed in Burma, Sri Lanka and the Philippines respectively (Falk 1997; Drewes 2007, 132; Orlina 2012). Note also a silver sheet with the *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* from Chaoyang North Pagoda; see Kim (in the present issue).
- 208 The *vā* at the end of this sentence is problematic, similarly to other variants with

-codana.

- 209 Although no terracotta sealings with the *Uṣṇīṣavijayā-dhāraṇī* are known to survive in South Asia, for recent research on *dhāraṇī* seals with texts including the *Vimaloṣṇīṣa-dhāraṇī* see Lama (2013) and cf. also Hidas (2021b).
- 210 Note that the Chinese and Tibetan versions do not mirror “it should be written on gold leaf and should be placed in a Dharma relic shrine after worshipping the Dharma relic respectfully. Having prepared wet clay [sealings], seven [times] twenty-one [or] forty, having worshipped these a hundred or a thousand times, they should be revered with parasols, banners, flowers, incense, lamps, fragrances, offerings and so on during all [kinds of] *pūjā*. One should recite this *dhāraṇī* called the Topknot Victory of all Tathāgatas. Finally, it should be honored with uncrushed *dūrvā* leaves at the top of a *caitya*. For whom [this is done], he will have an immeasurable lifespan” and there “according to one’s means” refers to the previously mentioned *pūjā*. Note also the longer omission at this place in manuscript D.
- 211 This sentence is not reflected in the Chinese and Tibetan versions.
- 212 The Chinese and Tibetan versions mirror “the one expected to live for seven days shall live for seven years.”
- 213 Note the formulaic ending (*idam avocad bhagavān...*) inserted in manuscripts B, D and I. Although it mentions Avalokiteśvara, Amitāyus does not feature in this sentence.

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